

A Magnetic Study of Colour Changes in Cobalt Chloride. Part II.

BY S. S. BHATNAGAR, A. N. KAPUR AND P. L. KAPUR.

The changes in the colour of solution of cobaltous chloride were first observed by Hellot (*Mem. Acad.*, 1737, 101, 228), Macquer ("Dictionnaire de Chimie, Neuchatel, 1789) and Proust (*J. Phys.*, 1806, 63, 364, 421). Since then these colour changes red $\rightleftharpoons$ blue of cobaltous chloride solutions have continued to excite interest as is shown by the voluminous literature published on the subject.

One of the earliest attempts made to explain these colour changes was to assume that the red colour is due to the existence of the hexahydrate in solution and that the blue colour is due to the formation of a lower hydrate. The hydration hypothesis as put forward, by several scientists,* though plausible, does not explain all the phenomena, as for example, the different effects produced by anhydrous calcium and zinc chlorides. This led Engel (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1888, ii, 50, 98; 1891, iii, 6, 240) to elaborate a molecular compound hypothesis. Engel assumed that the various colours are produced by the presence of double salts in solution. The hypothesis fits in with some of the facts but needs too many unproved subsidiary hypotheses to be satisfactory. Donnan and Bassett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 939) suggested an explanation based on the formation of complex ions. The complex-ion hypothesis assumes that in addition to the simple Co^{++} -ions and Cl^- -ions, there are also complex anions, e.g., CoCl_3^- and CoCl_4^{--} in equilibrium, such that the simple process of ionisation

* Von Babo (*Ber. Verh. Naturforsch. Ges. Freiburg*, 1858, 1, 277), Benrath (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 54, 328), Berthelot ("Thermochimie" Paris, 1897, 2, 298), Brown (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1912, 32, 50; 1912, 33, 44), Hartley (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Dublin*, 1900, ii, 7, 253; *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 19, 49) and Moore (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 58, 641).

is followed by

The non-ionised salt in solution is supposed to be blue, and the complex anion in solution is also blue, while the colour due to the cobalt atom when outside the immediate sphere of chlorine atoms, appears to be red. The different effects produced by anhydrous zinc and calcium chloride are explained on the fact that zinc having greater tendency to enter into negative complex groups, would form $\text{Co}(\text{ZnCl}_4)$, while the calcium double chloride will have the constitution $\text{Ca}(\text{CoCl}_4)$, since cobalt has a greater tendency to form negative complexes than calcium. The work of Denham and co-workers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, **65**, 641; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1353) on transport numbers, of Moore (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, **55**, 641), Job (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, **196**, 181; 1934, **198**, 827), Groh and Schmidt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **162**, 321) on absorption spectra and of Bessett and Croucher (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1784), on the equilibria of the complex salt of cobalt chloride with hydrochloric acid and mercuric, magnesium and zinc chlorides, favours the complex-ion hypothesis. Kotschubei (*J. Russ. Phys.-Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **46**, 1055) attributed the change in colour, not to the formation of CoCl_4' , but to the transition from the $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{++}$ -ion to the $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{++}$ -ion to

Bhatnagar and Kapur (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 341) determined the value of the Weiss magneton number for cobalt salts in aqueous solution and found it to be 25.04. For solutions of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methyl, ethyl and amyl alcohols, the Weiss magneton number varied between 22 and 23. In hydrochloric acid solutions, the value lay between 22 and 24. This effect was attributed, therefore, to the formation of $(\text{CoCl}_3)'$ and $(\text{CoCl}_4)''$ and not due to the production of anhydrous CoCl_2 or $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, as the Weiss magneton number for these salts as well as for CoCl_2 solutions in concentrated sulphuric acid was practically 25.

It is well known that the study of magneto-optic relations throws some light on the nature of ionic "micelle" in solution (*cf.* Bhatnagar and Kapur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 767). It was with this

view that the study of magneto-optic rotation of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in different solvents was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The method employed for the study of the magneto-optic rotation of the $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions in different solvents consisted in placing the water-jacketed tube (2.75 cm. long) containing the solution in a solenoid described in a previous paper from this laboratory (*cf.* Mathur and Kapur, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1952, 7, 15) and measuring the rotation produced as a result of magnetic field. A current of 9.5 amp. was passed. The source of light used was a glass mercury vapour lamp with blue filter.

In order to calculate the molecular rotation of a dissolved substance from the measured rotation of the solution, it is assumed that the dissolved substance and the solvent act independently of each other and that the measured rotation is composed additively from the rotation of these two. The assumption leads, therefore, to the following expression for molecular magnetic rotation of solution,

$$d_m = \frac{W \times M_1 \times 100}{W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \times S \times 18 \times a}$$

where w denotes the rotation of the solution, $W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, the rotation of water, S , the density of solution, a , the percentage of the substance present in the solution, and M_1 , the mol. wt. of the solute.

Then M , the molecular rotation of the solute = $d_m - \mu M_s$, where M_s is the molecular rotation of solvent (for water it is 1) and μ , the number of g. mol. of solvent per mol. of the dissolved substance.

When the solvent is not water, its molecular rotation

$$M_s = \frac{\tau_1}{\tau} \times \frac{M}{d \times m}$$

where τ_1 denotes the rotation due to solvent; τ , the rotation due to water; M , the mol. wt. of the solvent; d , the density of the solvent; and m , the mol. wt. of water.

It is to be expected that if the assumption mentioned above does not hold, the molecular rotation will vary with concentration.

Extra pure Kahlbaum's sample of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ free from nickel was used. The purity of hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and amyl alcohol was tested by comparing their molecular magnetic rotations with the values obtained by other workers (*cf.* Table I.)

TABLE I.
Molecular magnetic rotation

Compound.	as determined by the authors.	as given in literature.
Amyl alcohol	5.91	5.95 (Inter. Crit. Tables)
Sulphuric acid	2.32	2.315 (Perkin, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1886, 49, 777)
Hydrochloric acid	3.79	4.00 (Perkin, <i>ibid.</i> , 1889, 55, 680)

The results obtained for the molecular magnetic rotation of cobalt chloride are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Solvent,	a.	μ .	S.	$W/W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	M.		
Water	12.52	50.43	1.066	1.133	+ 10.87		
	8.36	79.12	1.046	1.088	+ 10.66		
	2.544	283.2	1.022	1.057	+ 10.30		
Amyl alcohol	3.05	45.81	0.8352	0.987	+ 3.06		
	3.442	40.21	0.844	0.943	- 9.14		
HCl	30.83%	2.180	50.36 221.9	HCl H ₂ O	1.169	1.296	- 45.00
		2.217	41.05 235.2	HCl H ₂ O	1.148	1.276	- 28.00
	19.7%	2.277	30.81 247.4	HCl H ₂ O	1.117	1.244	- 11.2
	13.5%	2.343	20.52 259.4	HCl H ₂ O	1.086	1.182	- 1.52

DISCUSSION

From the results it is clear that the value for molecular magnetic rotation varies with varying concentration. This effect is just noticeable in aqueous solutions, but becomes increasingly prominent in alcoholic and HCl solutions. If the ions in solution remain all of one kind, the molecular magnetic rotation will also remain constant. The fact that the molecular magnetic rotation of cobaltous chloride in alcoholic and HCl solutions varies with concentration, suggests the presence of different ionic carriers. Further, the fact that the colour of the cobaltous chloride solutions in alcohol and HCl also changes with concentration from blue-violet to pink points to the possibility of the magnetic and colour carriers being identical.

On examination of the results we see that the molecular magnetic rotation of cobalt chloride in amyl alcohol solution varies from 3.06 to -9.14 with concentration. In HCl solution the value varies between -1.52 to -45.0, while the value in aqueous solution is 10.58 to 0.3. If the change in colour had only been due to the production of anhydrous cobalt chloride, as suggested by Hartley (*loc. cit.*) and others, the value would have remained constant with change of concentration.

The molecular magnetic rotation for cobalt chloride in concentrated sulphuric acid came to be +1.8. Thus, even if we suppose as suggested by Vaillant (*Compt. rend.*, 1929, 189, 747; 1930, 190, 170), that the colour change is brought about both by changing the state of ionisation and by causing dehydration, it is clear from the above experiment that dehydration can be only responsible for bringing the value of molecular magnetic rotation down to +1.8, but the predominant factor is the formation of complex ions of the type $(\text{CoCl}_3)'$ and $(\text{CoCl}_4)''$ as suggested in a previous publication (*loc. cit.*).